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An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: Pax8-as1.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of Pax8-as1 as a candidate gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

Citations

1. Ramachandran, D., Wang, Y., Schuermann, P., Huelse, F., Mao, Q., Jentschke, M., Boehmer, G., Strauß, H.G., Hirchenhain, C., Schmidmayr, M. and Mueller, F., 2021. Association of genomic variants at PAX8 and PBX2 with cervical cancer risk. *International Journal of Cancer*, 149(4), pp.893-900.